

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes of nickel-, copper- and zinc(II) with 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and β -diketones

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Mixed ligand complexes of the types $[M(L)(L')]$ ($M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}$; $HL = 5\text{-bromosalicylaldehyde}$ and $HL' = \text{acetylacetone, benzoylacetone or dibenzoylmethane}$) and $[Ni(L)(L')(H_2O)_2]$ have been synthesized by 1 : 1 : 1 molar reactions of metal chlorides with two different carbonyl compounds.

We reported earlier mixed ligand complexes of alkaline earth metals with aldehydes, ketones and related ligands¹. However, the mixed ligand complexes of transition metals with substituted salicylaldehydes have not been reported so far. In the present paper mixed ligand complexes of the types $[M(L)(L')]$ and $[Ni(L)(L')(H_2O)_2]$, where $M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}$; $HL = 5\text{-bromosalicylaldehyde}$ (5-BrsalH) and $HL' = 2,4\text{-pentanedione}$ (acetylacetone, acacH), 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione (benzoylacetone, bzacH) or 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione (dibenzoylmethane, dbzmH) are described.

Results and discussion

The reactions of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} chlorides with 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and acetylacetone, benzoylacetone or dibenzoylmethane in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios have resulted in the formation of mixed ligand complexes (I or II).

The Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes (Table 1) are insoluble in water and most organic solvents but soluble in DMSO.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the mixed ligand complexes

Compd.	Colour	Decomp. temp. °C	Metal (%) : Found (Calcd.)
$[Ni(5\text{-Brsal})(acac)(H_2O)_2]$	Green	210–215	14.92 (14.91)
$[Ni(5\text{-Brsal})(bzac)(H_2O)_2]$	Green	168–175	12.95 (12.88)
$[Ni(5\text{-Brsal})(dbzm)(H_2O)_2]$	Green	160–164	11.26 (11.33)
$[Cu(5\text{-Brsal})(acac)]$	Grey	195–200	17.66 (17.53)
$[Cu(5\text{-Brsal})(bzac)]$	Grey	185–190	14.77 (14.97)
$[Cu(5\text{-Brsal})(dbzm)]$	Grey	190–195	13.01 (13.06)
$[Zn(5\text{-Brsal})(acac)]$	Yellow	123–127	17.88 (17.94)
$[Zn(5\text{-Brsal})(bzac)]$	Yellow	138–143	15.39 (15.34)
$[Zn(5\text{-Brsal})(dbzm)]$	Yellow	195–198	13.28 (13.39)

Molar conductance values ($1.8\text{--}7.0 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) of all the complexes indicate their non-electrolytic nature².

Infrared spectra : The mixed ligand complexes reveal strong absorption bands at $1600\text{--}1670 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (coordinated $\nu_{C=O}$). The $\nu_{C=O}$ band appears at 1675 cm^{-1} in 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and at 1724 cm^{-1} in acetylacetone and benzoylacetone³. Thus the shifting of $\nu_{C=O}$ to lower wavenumber supports the coordination of C=O group to the metal atom. Such a shift has been reported in the IR spectra of alkaline earth^{1,4} and transition metal^{3,5} complexes of such ligands. Strong bands at $1500\text{--}1580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of mixed ligand complexes may be assigned to C=C stretching modes⁶. Weak bands at $400\text{--}490 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which are absent in the free ligands, may be assigned to ν_{M-O} vibrations⁷.

Thermal analysis : Thermogram of $[Cu(5\text{-Brsal})(bzac)]$ shows no weight-loss in the range $100\text{--}220^\circ$, suggesting the absence of coordinated water molecules, which is confirmed by the absence of endothermic peak in DTA. In $[Ni(5\text{-Brsal})(acac)(H_2O)_2]$, the weight-loss observed at $100\text{--}180^\circ$

corresponds to two coordinated water molecules, which is confirmed by the sharp endothermic peak in DTA. The weight left corresponds to the metal oxides.

Magnetic moments : The μ_{eff} values (at ~ 300 K) for the Cu^{II} complexes (2.14–2.34 B.M.) are slightly higher than those expected for a d^9 -system⁸. This may be attributed to the incomplete quenching of the orbital contribution to the magnetic moment⁹ or to spin-orbit coupling¹⁰. For the Ni^{II} complexes, μ_{eff} values are observed in the range 3.21–4.21 B.M., suggesting distorted octahedral geometry. The μ_{eff} values higher than expected for two unpaired electrons may be due to ferromagnetic nature of the nickel(II) complexes or due to incomplete quenching of orbital angular momentum by the ligand field¹¹. Zinc(II) complexes are diamagnetic.

Electronic spectra : In the electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes, weak band at 751–757 nm may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ transition. The band at 418–438 nm may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition merged with charge transfer band¹². In case of Cu^{II} , the spectrum of each complex exhibits a broad band at 656–670 nm, suggesting square-planar geometry. This band does not show any sign of splitting and therefore it is concluded that all $d-d$ transitions expected for a square-planar Cu^{II} complex are lying within this broad band¹³. In all the complexes of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} , strong bands at 319–328 and ~ 370 nm may be due to intra-ligand transitions ($n \rightarrow \pi^*$ or $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$) and the band at 401–438 nm may be charge transfer band.

${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra : In free acetylacetone, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane, CH proton peak has been reported to appear at δ 5.54, 6.18 and 6.82, respectively¹⁴, and in the mixed ligand complexes of Zn^{II} with the corresponding β -diketones this peak is observed at δ 5.47, 6.01 and 6.71, respectively. In free acetylacetone and benzoylacetone, CH_3 protons have been reported to give a singlet at δ 1.99 and 2.19, respectively¹⁴ and in the Zn^{II} mixed ligand complexes of these β -diketones, these singlets are observed at δ 1.80 and 1.99, respectively. This upfield shift of CH and CH_3 protons in the Zn^{II} complexes confirms the coordination of β -diketone ligands to zinc atom¹⁵. In free 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, the CHO proton gives a singlet at δ 10.34 which is shifted upfield in the mixed ligand complexes of Zn^{II} (δ 9.98–10.04), confirming the coordination of C=O group of the aldehyde residue to zinc atom.

Experimental

5-Bromosalicylaldehyde (Aldrich), benzoylacetone

(Fluka) and dibenzoylmethane (Sisco) were purified by crystallization from hot ethanol. Acetylacetone (K. Light) and ethanol were purified by distillation. $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ZnCl_2 and $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (all Fluka) were of A.R. grade.

Ni, Cu and Zn were determined by standard methods¹⁶. Conductance was measured (in $\sim 10^{-3}$ M DMSO) on a Systronics 304 instrument. Magnetic moment was measured on a Gouy balance. TG and DTA studies were carried out in Chemistry Department, University of Delhi, Delhi. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (DMSO) on a Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer and ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Zeol FX 90Q FT NMR spectrometer using TMS as a reference.

Mixed ligand complexes : To the ethanolic solution of Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} chloride (3.4 mmol in ~ 10 ml ethanol), an ethanolic solution of two different carbonyl compounds (3.4 mmol each in ~ 10 ml ethanol) was added with stirring. The pH of the reaction mixture was raised to ~ 5.5 by adding 5% aq. NaOH with stirring. Stirring was continued for 3–4 h and the products formed were washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

The Zn^{II} complexes were prepared similarly except using aq. ammonia solution in place of aq. NaOH.

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